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Effect of Tax Sheltering on Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of tax sheltering on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria. Using effective tax rate (ETR) as proxy of tax sheltering with control variables such as operating cash flow (OPC), financial leverage (FLVR), and firm age (LFAGE) and total investment expenditure as proxy of corporate investment expenditure. The study used *ex-post facto* research design, data used were sourced from published audited annual financial statements and annual reports of the selected listed financial firms in Nigeria, covering the forty-nine (49) financial services firms in Nigeria as of that 31 December, 2022. Using purposive sampling techniques, the selected ten (10) commercial banks, two (2) mortgage banks and eight firms from insurance and reinsurance sector that have been actively operating from 2012-2022. Data were analysed using descriptive analysis, Pearson correlation, and other diagnostic test such as, Stationarity and Cointegration, Heteroskedasticity, Model Mis, VIF, Serial Autocorrelation and Hausman Test and panel regression analysis. The findings revealed that effective tax rate exerted a statistically significant negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria, since the p-value > 0.05 at 0.000, and t-statistic < |2| at -5.40. The study suggests that effective tax rate of the financial firms should be monitored in relation to the statutory tax rate to ensure that it does not increase significantly.

Keywords: Corporate investment expenditure, Effective tax rate, Financial leverage, Operating cash flow, Tax sheltering

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Corporate managers should strive to increase the value of the company for the benefit of its shareholders, according to previous research in management and business (Jensen & Meckling, 1976 in Nicholson & Kiel, 2004). The story has shifted considering new research on corporate governance and sustainability, two areas that have emerged as central to modern theories of corporate management. Businesses today are expected to generate long-term value for all stakeholders (Lanis & Richardson, 2012; Karami & Rekabdar, 2020). Managers of these companies should prioritise the interests of all stakeholders (Ingrid, 2017; Igbru & orife, 2024). Corporate managers, according to this stakeholder approach, should treat their company's internal and external stakeholders fairly. Shareholders, workers, and executives are examples of internal stakeholders, whereas the government, suppliers, and host communities are examples of

external stakeholders. This indicates that for-profit businesses no longer have wealth building or profit maximisation as their primary goal.

Tax sheltering comprises a wide range of acts with the express objective to lower tax (expenses) burden. (Dyrenge et al., 2016; Edwards et al., 2016; Gebhart, 2017; Ogbeide & Iyafekhe, 2018; Dyrenge & Maydew, 2018; Martinez et al., 2019, Obasi, et al., 2020, Anyaduba & Ogbeide, 2022; Delgado et al., 2023). Tax sheltering is a legitimate activity if it is undertaken within the range of the law (Obasi et al. 2020). For an organization to implement efficient tax planning or sheltering practices, the managers must be knowledgeable in tax law and administration, audit and have expertise. In the view of Bonner et al. (1992) in Kportorgbi et al. (2018) the managers must possess cognitive skills and personal dispositions. These skills include that the managers must be able to understand the tax legislation; discover (opportunity) gaps in the tax law, define consistent and successive plans to exploit the opportunities, and implement the scheme.

Previous studies have employed numerous financial statement indicators to estimate the amount of tax avoidance in corporate organizations. The first construct are metrics based on the percentage of tax amount to business income that is, the effective tax rate (ETR). ETR is a measure of actual tax expenses faced by the taxpayer (Salawu et al., 2017; Osegbue et al., 2018; Rani et al., 2018; Ebubechukwu & Obada, 2021).

Generally, the difference in interest's from the government is to expect huge and consistently increasing tax revenues each year, and of course opposite to the interests of corporations that want to pay as minimum tax as possible. Consequently, company managers do engage in numerous strategic tax planning efforts. They have been named tax sheltering, tax avoidance, tax planning, tax minimization or tax aggression in the legal form or tax evasion in the fraudulent aspect. From this perspective, these activities capture two limitations, tax preferred transactions (legal practices) on one end and aggressive behaviours (illegal practices) on the other end, throwing up complexity in determining practices that are legal, optimal and illegal.

In Nigeria, businesses are challenged with the issues of various taxations, ineffective administrative tax systems, high tax rates, unfriendly tax laws and other operating expenditures that endanger their survival and the going-concern status of their operations. Most of this research have focused heavily on the non-financial sector like manufacturing enterprises. Again, the question relating to the degree to which cash flow from tax sheltering enhances company investment expenditure has been highlighted. Based on the foregoing the study focus examined the effect of tax sheltering on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria using effective tax rate as a proxy of tax sheltering on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Tax sheltering is one of the concepts that have emerged in the research of tax evasion (Mieseigha & Okewale, 2021). They observed that the phrase has been used interchangeably with tax aggressiveness, planning, avoidance, and reduction (Dyrenge et al., 2016; Edwards et al., 2016; Gebhart, 2017; Ogbeide & Iyafekhe, 2018; Delgado et al., 2023).

Lee et al. (2015) defines a tax shelter as any method used by taxpayers to reduce taxable revenue without legitimate business reasons. According to Evers et al. (2016), tax aggression demands some level of complexity to avoid detection by companies; yet the goal is to maximise company value and performance. Dyrenge and Maydew (2018) defined tax avoidance as any decrease in pretax accounting income. Tax sheltering refers to the actions used by taxpayers to reduce their tax burden to generate higher after-tax earnings per share and increased cash flow for shareholders (Osegbue et al. 2018). Martinez et al. (2019) defined tax aggressiveness as a broad set of measures aimed solely at reducing an organization's total tax debt or burden. Obasi et al. (2020) described tax aggressiveness as a method of lowering the tax burden through enterprises' tax strategies.

Kumbour et al. (2017) specifically said that tax-minimizing efforts include forecasting situations and identifying opportunities within the current tax law framework to reduce or defer tax payments. As a

result, Obasi et al. (2020) argue that it remains acceptable when functioning within the scope of the law and unethical when affecting the integrity of the tax system. As a result, our analysis will be consistent with the definition provided by Anyaduba and Ogbeide (2022), who defined corporate tax aggressiveness as a word that encompasses all behaviours and activities (legal or rational) that a firm engages in with the goal of optimising their tax burden. In recent years, scholars and policymakers have used a variety of measures based on financial statement estimates to quantify the level of tax sheltering, aggressiveness, avoidance, and tax planning in commercial organisations. Ogbeide and Iyafekhe (2018) classified these measures as three categories. According to them, one group designs the arrangements that determine the proportion of tax revenue to corporate income. These include Dyreng et al.'s (2008) effective tax rate (ETR), which has many variations, including accounting ETR, current ETR, cash ETR, long-run cash ETR, ETR difference, the ratio of income tax expense to operational cash flow, and the ratio of cash taxes paid to operating cash flow.

Effective Tax Rate (ETR)

The effective tax rate (ETR) is computed by discounting total tax expenses against pretax income (Aliani & Zarai, 2012). The effective tax rate can also be referred to as the IFRS effective tax rate (ETR). The effective tax rate is derived by dividing total tax expenses by income before tax, revealing the proportion of accounting income that is taxed (Chen et al., 2010; Dyreng et al., 2010; Salihu et al., 2013). It also measures the average tax rate per unit of profits. The adoption of an effective tax rate demonstrates firms' extensive tax preparation via lasting book-tax differences. According to Lee et al. (2015), comparing the computed IFRS (ETR) to the statutory rate or a control rate to measure tax aggressiveness indicates the level of tax hiding. They claim that the IFRS (ETR) indicates permanent book-tax differences from statutory corrections since total income tax expenses contain both current and deferred tax expenses.

A company's tax plan for delaying tax payments does not affect IFRS (ETR). With the use of IFRS (ETR), aggregate income tax does not always imply a tax liability. This is due to accrual adjustments, such as changes in account valuation, which effect book income but not taxable income (Olufemi & Olori). IFRS (ETR) can be translated into current ETR by adding current tax expenses to the numerator (Hanlon & Shevlin, 2002). By putting current expenses in the numerator, the effect of the deferred tax technique can be minimized. However, Lee et al. (2015) noticed that the ETR technique is subject to accrual adjustments, below-the-line items, and the non-qualified stock option, among other things.

Some research has further proxies effective tax rate using income tax expense divided by operating cash flow, the ratio of cash taxes paid to operating cash flow, effective tax rate (ETR) differentials, and current reported tax divided by profit before tax (Desai & Dharmapala, 2008; Chen et al., 2010; Aliani & Zarai, 2012; Zemzem & Flouhi, 2013; Bousaidi & Hamed, 2015; Oyeleke et al., 2016). Others have adopted the cash-effective tax rate (CETR). The cash ETR is determined by deducting the cash tax paid from the taxable income (Chen et al., 2010). They also asserted that cash ETR is a measure of the tax rate per dollar of income earned. This measure has the advantage of being unaffected by accrual adjustments, except for deferred strategies. Similarly, the periods connected with taxes paid, specifically the numerator, and pretax book income, in this case the denominator, do not have to be constant. Tax expenses may be incurred because of both current and prior year revenue; however, book income must be created in the current year. As a result, the cash ETR appears flexible, conforming to the goal of capturing listed firms' tax aggressiveness when compared to the IFRS effective tax rate (ETR), despite its limitations, which stem primarily from timing differences between the years in which income was earned and related taxes were paid (Aliani and Zarai, 2012). Thus, the following hypothesis was formulated and tested: H_{01} : *effective tax rate has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.*

Theoretical Review

The study is anchored on stakeholder theory.

The Stakeholder Theory

Freeman introduced the stakeholder's hypothesis in his book *Strategic Management: a Stakeholder Approach*, which was first published in 1984. The theory was proposed in response to growing concern

about the long-term viability of a firm's focus on shareholders' money as its primary goal. The stakeholder's thesis believes that shareholders do not represent a firm's only interest, and that organisations must identify and model the groups that constitute its stakeholders to properly respect those groups' interests. Other contributors to this hypothesis include Harry (2007, 2009), Jeff (2011), and Robert (2011), among others.

The importance of this concept to the current inquiry cannot be overstated. In terms of internal governance, the stakeholders' approach demands Boards to consider the needs of an increasing number of stakeholder groups, including interest groups focused on social, environmental, and ethical issues (Ogbechie, 2012). In relation to the current study, the theory suggests that the most fundamental goal of business is to create value for all three interest groups (customers, employees, and investors), not just shareholders. As a result, this theoretical approach emphasises the importance of incorporating all stakeholders into the board's management strategy.

Empirical Review

Ebubechukwu and Obada (2021) conducted another study to evaluate the association between tax preparation and the financial success of Nigerian listed food and beverage companies. From 2009 to 2019, six firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group's (NXG) floor were selected for the study. The target variable was return on assets (ROA), with the effective tax rate (ETR) as the regressor. Firm size was used as a control variable. Multiple panel data regression was used for data analysis. The analysis found that the relationship between effective tax rate and firm size is statistically insignificant.

Fagbemi et al. (2019) conducted a similar investigation of the corporate tax planning and financial performance of Nigeria's systemically important banks. The study measured performance using return on equity, whereas indicators of corporate tax planning included effective tax rate (ETR), income tax expense scaled by pre-tax earnings, capital intensity (CAPINT), total debts to total assets ratio, leasing arrangement possibilities, and firm size. The pooled OLS regression was used for data analysis. The results revealed that the effective tax rate had a significant negative effect on profitability; the total debts to total assets ratio had a positive significant influence on performance; and the effect of the other variable measures in the study was statistically non-significant.

Kasim and Saad (2019) explored the elements that contribute to corporate tax avoidance among Malaysian multinational corporations. The study used a panel data analysis technique on 830 firm-year observable data obtained from the Malaysian Inland Revenue Board. The effective tax rate served as a proxy for tax evasion, while the regressors were profit before tax and interest (PTI), capital intensity, financial leverage, foreign operations, and firm size. According to the research, profit before tax and interest, overseas operations, and financial leverage all have a negative impact on the effective tax rate, whereas company size has a positive and significant impact on the effective tax rate, and capital intensive has no noticeable impact on the effective tax rate.

Ifurueze et al. (2018) examined the impact of strategic tax aggression on the growth of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria between 2007 and 2016. The study uses earnings after tax as a proxy for corporate growth, using effective tax rate (ETR) and leverage (LEV) as independent variables. The Pooled OLS results indicated that LEV and ETR were not statistically significant in explaining differences in the regressor.

Rani et al. (2018) investigated the moderating influence of profit management on the association between tax avoidance and firm characteristics using a sample of 49 listed manufacturing organisations on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2012 to 2016. The panel data regression technique (Random Effect Model [REM]) was used in this investigation. The effective tax rate (Tax/PBT) was used to measure tax evasion. The independent variables were profitability (ROA) and debt-equity ratio, while the control variable was firm size (SIZE). Earnings management was documented using discretionary accruals (DA) as dissected by function (ROA*DA, DER*DA, SIZE*DA). The findings revealed that ROA, SIZE, and DER*DA were statistically significant but had a negative impact on ETR; DER and ROA*DA had a statistically significant positive effect on ETR, but the effects of DA and SIZE*DA on ETR were not significant.

Kurawa and Saidu (2018) used panel data analysis on a dataset acquired from 16 selected companies to analyse the relationship between corporation tax and the financial performance of listed consumer products businesses on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG) from 2006 to 2016. Return on assets was used as a proxy for financial performance (dependent variable), whereas the independent variables were effective tax rate (ETR), firm size (SIZE), age (AGE), and risk (RISK). The results showed that ETR, AGE, and RISK had no significant association with ROA, whereas SIZE did.

Deméré et al. (2017) conducted an empirical examination of the relationship between smoothing activities and high or bad financial reporting quality from 1996 to 2012. The study's dependent variable was discretionary accrual (DA), with regressors including effective tax rate, profitability, leverage, research and development expense, foreign income-producing activity, capital intensity, intangible assets, mergers and acquisitions, cash holdings and losses marked-to-book, and net operating loss carryforwards. They conducted an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression to examine. The study found that the effective tax rate has a statistically significant negative affect on discretionary accruals, implying that the effective tax rate acts as a mediator between the level of financial reporting quality and earning quality, either increasing or decreasing.

Irianto et al. (2017) used a sample of 36 listed manufacturing firms on the Indonesian Stock Exchange from 2013 to 2015 to study the variables of tax avoidance. Data were analysed using a panel regression analytical approach. The effective tax rate was used as a proxy for tax evasion, and the dependent variables were capital intensity, company size, profitability, and leverage. The findings revealed that, whereas capital intensity, profitability, and leverage had no significant positive association with tax avoidance, business size did.

Salawu et al. (2017) used a VAR Granger Causality test to determine the relationship between tax planning and the value of firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG) from 2004 to 2014. Tax planning was represented by the effective tax rate (ETR), and business value was assessed using Tobin's Q. The results of the pairwise VAR Granger Causality test revealed no directional relationship between tax planning and firm value.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted *ex-post facto* research design because it provides empirical solutions to research problems by using data that are already in existence. The study focuses on Nigeria, sourcing data from the published audited annual financial statements and annual reports of the selected listed financial firms in Nigeria. The population of the study consist of the forty-nine (49) financial services firms in Nigeria as of 31st Dec., 2022. Using purposive sampling techniques, the selected ten (10) commercial banks, two (2) mortgage banks and eight firms from insurance and reinsurance sector that have been actively operating from 2012-2022.

Model Specification

The fundamental model for this study will take its shape from the classical linear regression (CLR) form of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \mu_t \quad - \quad (3.1)$$

Using the present research variables, the model in equation 3.1 above is presented as follows:

$$TIE_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ETR_t + \mu_t \quad - \quad (3.2)$$

Where: TIE_t = Total Investment Expenditure at time t, ETR_t = Effective Tax Rate at time t,

β_0 = Constants, β_1 = Coefficient of the independent variables in the model, μ_t = Stochastic error associated with the model.

Introducing the control variables, the model in equation 3.2 above is presented as follows:

$$TIE_t = \beta_o + \beta_1 ETR_t + \beta_2(OPC/TA)_t + \beta_3 FLVE_t + \beta_4 LnFAGE_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

Where: OPC/TA_t = Operating Cash Flow deflated by Total Assets at time t, $FLVR_t$ = Financial Leverage at time t, $LnFAGE_t$ = Natural Logarithm Firm age at time t, Other variables in the model retain their original meaning.

Robustness test was carried out using New Investment Expenditure and Investment Maintenance Expenditure as the dependent variable. The model is form as:

$$NIE_t = \beta_o + \beta_1 ETR_t + \beta_2(OPC/TA)_t + \beta_3 FLVE_t + \beta_4 LnFAGE_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3.4)$$

$$IME_t = \beta_o + \beta_1 ETR_t + \beta_2(OPC/TA)_t + \beta_3 FLVE_t + \beta_4 LnFAGE_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots (3.5)$$

Other variables in the model retain their original meaning.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 4.1: Summary Statistics of Variables for the Financial Firms in Nigeria

<i>stats</i>	<i>tie</i>	<i>ime</i>	<i>etr</i>
Summary Stats			
Minimum	0.0102	0.0009	-7.9583
Maximum	0.4459	0.0468	0.8809
Mean	0.0992	0.0066	0.0768
Median	0.0559	0.0046	0.1466
Standard Deviation (SD)	0.0977	0.0058	0.6181
SE(Mean)	0.0066	0.0004	0.0417
Normality Test			
Skewness	1.8793	3.5142	-10.6890
Pr(Skewness)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Kurtosis	5.8621	21.8061	134.0882
Pr(Kurtosis)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
----- joint -----			
chi2(2)	64.1700	-	-
Prob>chi2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Shapiro-Wilk W test (
Prob>z)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.1 depicts the summary statistics conducted on the data. The “Overall” statistics are ordinary statistics that are based on 220 observations. The mean and the median of the variables, the powerful statistical measures of mid-point even though vulnerable to extreme values of the listed twenty (20) financial firms in Nigeria in two hundred and twenty (220) observations were computed. The closeness between the mean and median in almost all the variables particularly the explanatory variables suggest the existence of uniformity in the performance of the financial firms in Nigeria which indicates that the disparity in the sizes of the firms has no effect on their tax management performance, indicating no

material extreme values. On the other hand, the standard deviation, a measure of dispersion is not large suggesting that annual values of each of the variables are very close to the mid-point.

Also, normality tests were performed to determine whether a data set is modeled for normal distribution. Skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of the probability distribution of a random variable about its mean. In other words, it shows the amount and direction of skew (departure from horizontal symmetry).

Pearson Correlations

The Pearson correlation coefficients measure the degree of relationship between the different variables.

Table 4.2. Correlation Matrix with P-values involving 220 Observations

	<i>tie</i>	<i>lme</i>	<i>etr</i>	<i>flvr</i>	<i>lnfa</i>
<i>tie</i>	1.0000				
<i>ime</i>	0.7190*	1.0000			
	0.0000				
<i>etr</i>	-0.1011	-0.2252*	1.0000		
	0.1350	0.0008			
<i>flvr</i>	-0.7467*	-0.6223*	0.1165	1.0000	
	0.0000	0.0000	0.0848		
<i>lnfa</i>	0.1695*	0.2247*	-0.1304	-0.1225	1.0000
	0.0118	0.0008	0.0534	0.0697	

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.2 effective tax rate, financial leverage and the natural logarithm of firm age displayed a strong association with investment maintenance expenditure. Effective tax rate, and financial leverage have strong negative association with investment maintenance expenditure.

Diagnostic Tests for Stationarity and Cointegration

Unit roots are one cause of non-stationarity. Unit roots test is a test for stationarity in a time series.

Table 4.3 Levin-Lin-Chu unit-root test Based on Based on Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests

Variables	Unadjusted t	Adjusted t*	p-value	Lags
	<i>Statistics</i>	<i>Statistics</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>ADF regressions</i>
Tie	-24.8551	-18.7304	0.0000	3
Ime	-11.8000	-4.0483	0.0001	1
Etr	-16.0771	-10.6635	0.0153	3
Ocf	-15.5848	-8.4760	0.0000	1
Flvr	-36.2706	-33.5206	0.0000	3
Lnage	-14.1844	-11.2943	0.0000	1

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.3 depicts the outcome of the Levin-Lin Chu unit-root test based on augmented Dickey-Fuller tests carried out on the data at lag 1 to 3. The results of this test statistics strongly reject the null hypothesis that the panels contain unit-roots for all the entered variables at lag 1-3. Therefore, the study concludes that the data for all variables in the study are stationary.

Diagnostic Test for Heteroskedasticity

Table 4.4: Breusch-Pagan Test for Heteroskedasticity (All-Inclusive Model)

Ho: Constant variance			
Variables: fitted values of	tieta	tieta	imeta
chi2(1)	=	116.74	207.47
Prob > chi2	=	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.4 depicts the Breusch-Pagan test result for heteroskedasticity for the model specification. Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test was employed to ascertain whether the standard deviation of the data over the period is statistically constant (heteroskedasticity problem). Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test assumes the p-value of above the significant levels to be free from heteroskedasticity problem among the datasets.

Test for Model Mis – Specification

Table 4.5: Ramsey RESET Mis-specification Test

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of eps			
Ho: model has no omitted variables			
		tieta	imeta
F(3, 208)	=	18.01	18.57
Prob > F	=	0.0000	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.5 presents the outcome of Ramsey Reset test used to ascertain if the comprehensive model is appropriately specified i.e., over or under fitted. The result of these test shows $F(3, 208) = 18.01$ and 18.57 with P-values (0.0000) which implies that the model is not over-specified.

Test for Multi-collinearity

Multicollinearity is an unsteady condition of the regression model, estimates, and over-bloated standard errors for the coefficient (Gujarati and Porter, 2009). The variance inflation factor measures the degree of the (strong) linear relationship between one predictor variable and one or more explanatory variables. As a rule of thumb, Montgomery and Peck (2007) suggested $5 < VIF < 10$. This implies that VIFs value between 1 and 5 is moderate but above 5 is severe.

Table 4.6 Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
flvr	1.21	0.825739
lnfa	1.14	0.877631
etr	1.08	0.924181
ocf	1.06	0.944081
Mean VIF		4.35

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

A test of multicollinearity was conducted using the variance inflation factor approach (VIF) as depicted in Table 4.7. In this instance, the explanatory variables have resultant variance inflation factors ranging between 1.06 and 1.21 and a mean VIF of $4.35 < 5.0$ for the comprehensive model.

Diagnostic Test for Serial Autocorrelation

Serial autocorrelation is the statistical description of the extent to which values of the same variables correlate across different observations over time.

Table 4.7 Wooldridge test (All-Inclusive Model)

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data				
Ho: no first-order autocorrelation				
F(1, 7)	=	93.064		1845.54
Prob > F	=	0.0000		0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Further, the Wooldridge tests of serial autocorrelation in panel data were carried out. The Wooldridge tests assumed a null hypothesis of no first-order autocorrelation. In this instance, Table 4.7 depicts the outcome of the test. The result reveals a non-significant p-value (Prob > F = 0.0000) which is less than 0.05 significant levels indicating that the panel data is not free from first-order autocorrelation. Hence, we upheld the alternative hypothesis. Nevertheless, it was resolved by conducting a regression model that adjusted for first-order autocorrelation (ar1).

Diagnostic of Test for Heteroskedasticity in Panel Data

Table 4.8. Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test for Random effects

	Var	sd = sqrt(Var)		
Tieta	.0095529	.0977389		
E	.0010871	.0329716		
U	.0010849	.0329376		
Test: Var(u) = 0				
			chibar2 (01) =	340.80
			Prob > chibar2 =	0.0000

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

The Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test doubles as the test for the presence of panel heteroskedasticity and test to facilitate the decision between the *Random Effects Model (REM)* and the *Pooled Ordinary Least Square (POLS)*. The Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier (LM) test has the null hypothesis that variances across entities are zero which means no statistically significant difference across units (no panel effect). The decision rule is that if the Breusch Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (LM) result is significant at 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis will be rejected.

As depicted in table 4.8, the result of this test shows $chi^2(1) = 340.80$ and $Prob > chibar^2 = 0.0000$. The result shows the null hypothesis is rejected as it is strongly significant at the 5% level of significance, which implies that the random effect model is appropriate for the model estimation. Therefore, the *Random Effect Model (REM)* is better.

Fixed and Random Effects Tests of Model Estimation

Table 4.9: Hausman Test of All-Inclusive Model Validity

Variable	(b) fe	(B) Re	(b-B) Difference	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B)) S.E.
etr	-0.005144	-0.006203	0.001059	0.045259
ocf	0.0281372	0.0235908	0.0045464	0.030029
flvr	-0.0771574	-0.1616139	0.0844565	0.0059191
lnfa	-0.0160179	-0.0001993	-0.0158186	0.0040423

b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtreg
 B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtreg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\chi^2(8) = (b-B)'[(V_b - V_B)^{-1}](b-B) = 129.44$$

$$\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$$

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

Table 4.9 facilitates a choice between the *Fixed Effects Model (FEM)* and the *Random Effects Model (REM)*. The Hausman test has the null hypothesis that the preferred model is fixed effects vs the alternative fixed effect. The Hausman test results show $\chi^2(8) = 129.44$ and $\text{Prob.} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$ which suggest that the fixed effect model is not appropriate therefore strengthens the decision that the *Random Effect Model (REM)* is the most appropriate model for the panel dataset.

Model Estimation

The random effect (RE) regression model assumes that the variation across entities is random and uncorrelated with the predictor or regressor included in the model.

Table 4.10: Panel Regression Results of Tax Sheltering Indicators, Control Variables and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial firms in Nigeria

Regressors		Method	Pooled OLS	Fixed Effect	Random Effect (Recommended Model)	PCSEs (Preferred Model)
etr	p-value		0.779	0.202	0.178	0.000*
	t-statistic		0.28	-1.28	-1.35	-3.61
	coefficient		-.0020655	-0.005144	-0.006203	-.0026085
ocf	p-value		0.081	0.315	0.426	0.152
	t-statistic		-1.75	1.01	0.74	-1.43
	coefficient		-0.0886617	0.0281372	0.0235908	-.0113669
flvr	p-value		0.000*	0.001*	0.000*	0.000*
	t-statistic		-14.97	-3.36	-7.30	-18.51
	coefficient		-0.3049537	-0.0771574	-0.1616139	-.1652166
infa	p-value		0.11	0.062	0.979	0.000*
	t-statistic		1.61	-1.88	-0.03	6.19
	coefficient		0.0092339	-0.0160179	-0.0001993	.0102448
_cons	p-value		0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.000
	t-statistic		10.95	6.64	7.02	22.42
	Coefficient		0.2848017	0.2054517	0.2121882	.177882
<i>R-Squared</i>			57.67	0.2615	0.5479	0.3877
<i>F-statistic (Prob)/ Wald chi2 (Prob)</i>			35.93 (0.0000)	3.31(0.0015)	59.16 (0.0000)	38.06 (0.0000)
<i>rho (fraction of variance due to u_i)</i>				.87062491	.49943843	
<i>Poolability Test (Breusch-Pagan LM)</i>					340 (0.0000)	
<i>Hausman test</i>				129.44 (0.0000)		
Original Durbin-Watson statistic				2.04		
No of Observations = 220				Number of Firms = 20		
<i>Dependent Variable: KCE, significant at *1%, **5%, t-statistics</i>						

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

The study employed the *Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) Model adjusted Autocorrelation (AR 1) statistics, Panel-level heteroskedastic and correlated across panels* to correct the positive first-order autocorrelation (ar1) as identified in the Wooldridge tests, multicollinearity as identified in the variance inflation factor and heteroskedasticity as indicated by the Breusch-Pagan test and Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test.

From the statistics above, the R-squared (the multiple coefficients of determination) is 0.3877. In specific terms, it suggests that 38.77% of changes in total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria can be explained by the regressors (*effective tax rate operating cash flows, financial leverage, and natural logarithm of firm age*). However, the F-statistics = 38.06 and Prob. = 0.0000 is lower than = 0.05 which strengthens the overall statistical significance and reinforces the relevance of the predictors in the model. This also means that the 38.77% explanatory power of the regressors is statistically significant in explaining changes in the total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Hence, this model is best fitted to explain the relationship between the regressors and the regressand included in the model. However, the regressors (*effective tax rate, financial leverage, and natural logarithm of firm age*) exhibited significant effect on the total investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria as can be deduced from the coefficient and *p-values* $0.0000 < 0.05$.

Robustness Tests of the Model

Robustness tests were carried out using investment maintenance expenditure as the regressor.

Table 4.11: Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) using Investment Maintenance Expenditure (IME) as the Regressand

Panel-corrected						
Variables	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Etr	-0.000722	0.000275	2.62	0.009	-0.001261	-0.000182
Btd	-0.621013	1.783506	0.35	0.728	-4.116620	2.874595
Tbd	-16.911630	6.767604	2.50	0.012	-30.175890	-3.647370
Pbd	-1.688577	0.676802	2.49	0.013	-3.015084	-0.362070
Ts	7.636584	5.229276	1.46	0.144	-2.612608	17.885780
Ocf	0.001429	0.002398	0.60	0.551	-0.003270	0.006129
Flvr	-0.006772	0.002319	2.92	0.004	-0.011317	-0.002226
Lnfa	0.001651	0.000479	3.45	0.001	0.000712	0.002590
_cons	0.006274	0.001768	3.55	0.000	0.002808	0.009739

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

The summarized results of the robustness check conducted using investment maintenance expenditure as the regressand are depicted in Table 4.11.

From the statistics above, the R-squared (the multiple coefficients of determination) is 0.2538. In specific terms, it suggests that 25.38% of changes in investment maintenance expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria can be explained by the regressors (*effective tax rate, operating cash flows, financial leverage, and natural logarithm of firm age*). However, the F-statistics = 28.93 and Prob. = 0.0003 is lower than = 0.05 which strengthens the overall statistical significance and reinforces the relevance of the predictors in the model. This also means that the 25.38% explanatory power of the regressors is statistically significant in explaining changes in the investment maintenance expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Effective tax rate has no significant effect on corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Table 4.12: Multiple Regression, Correlated Panels Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) of Tax Sheltering Indicators and Corporate Investment Expenditure of Listed Financial Firms in Nigeria

Panel-corrected						
Variables	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Etr	-0.000606	0.000112	-5.40	0.000	-0.000826	-0.000386
Ocf	0.000485	0.001346	0.36	0.718	-0.002152	0.003123
Flvr	-0.005318	0.000762	-6.98	0.000	-0.006812	-0.003824
Lnfa	0.001312	0.000253	5.18	0.000	0.000816	0.001809
_cons	0.006238	0.000903	6.91	0.000	0.004469	0.008008

Source: STATA 14.2 Outputs, 2026

From table 4.12, the coefficient (β) indicates that a unit change in account effective tax rate will translate to -0.000606 increases in the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria. Specifically, effective tax rate exhibited a very strong negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the firms with a p-value = 0.000. However, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that effective tax rate exerted a statistically significant negative effect on the corporate investment expenditure of the listed financial firms in Nigeria, since the p-value > 0.05 at 0.000, and t-statistic < |2| at -5.40.

5.0 CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the findings, the study concludes that the effective tax rate (ETR), is significant predictors of corporate investment expenditure of listed financial firms in Nigeria and tax sheltering practices could be used to boost business growth opportunities and expansion in the listed financial firms in Nigeria when practiced within the provisions of the law. Based on the forgoing the study suggests as follows:

- i. Effective tax rate of the financial firms should be monitored in relation to the statutory tax rate to ensure that it does not increase significantly.

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